

Purpose Tasks And Characteristics Of Conducting Integrated Lessons In Primary Classes

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the purpose, tasks and features of conducting integrated lessons in primary grades.

Keywords — integrated lesson, conceptual interdisciplinary relations, symmetry, interdisciplinary communication, assignment, logical assignment.

INTRODUCTION.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the management system of public education" No. PF-5538, as the main directions of reforming the public education system, introduction of advanced foreign experience into the educational system, modern pedagogical technologies, including innovative methods of teaching, creation of a new generation of educational and pedagogical literature, fundamental and applied scientific research the importance of implementation is determined. In order to ensure the implementation of this decree, approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 "On measures to introduce new principles of management into the public education system" No. PQ-3931 "in 2018-2021 In the program of measures for the further improvement of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan: improvement of new state educational standards and curricula of general secondary education and at the same time STEM (S - science - natural science, T – technology, Ye – engineering, M – mathematics) education has been defined.

Based on the implementation of the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Natural Science" textbook for primary school students and a methodological manual for primary school teachers, i.e. "Teacher's Book", were created. Starting from the 2021-2022 academic year, teaching of "Natural Sciences" has been implemented in the 1st and 2nd grades of general secondary education schools in our republic.

Recently, in the theory and practice of primary education, optimal options for teaching individual subjects are being sought. In this regard, various forms of studying the knowledge system are being developed.

The task of forming a comprehensive vision of the world and the place of a person in it from the age of primary school is one of the urgent tasks set before the future primary school teachers.

One way to solve this problem is integrated education.

Primary education has its own characteristics that sharply distinguish it from all subsequent stages of school education. During this period, educational activities are conducted on the basis of fundamentals, cognitive interests and cognitive motivation.

The problem of introducing the integration of sciences into education is aimed at solving issues of this nature. Studies show that interdisciplinary communication plays an initial stimulating role in the stages of students' participation in educational activities.

The knowledge gained as a result of previous experience becomes the regulator of his cognitive activity.

Today, integration defines a person's scientific way of thinking and worldview. The following interpretation of these concepts is given in the philosophical dictionary:

Integration is an aspect of the development process that deals with the integration of previously disparate parts and elements into a whole. Instead, it is a scientific and logical connection of several independent sciences.

What is the essence of integration in education?

In relation to the educational system, "integration" as a concept can have two meanings:

- creating a holistic view of schoolchildren about the world (where integration is considered as the goal of education);
- to find a common unity to combine knowledge acquired in different disciplines (here, integration is a learning tool).

Therefore, the integrated lesson is aimed at creating the foundations of a holistic view of nature and society, forming one's attitude to the laws of their development.

Therefore, it is important for a young student to look at an object or phenomenon of reality from different angles: logically and emotionally, in a work of art and a scientific article, from the point of view of a biologist or an artist.

The methodological basis of the integrated approach is the establishment of intra-subject and inter-subject relationships in mastering the basics of science and understanding the laws of everything that exists in the world. And this should be a condition for repeatedly returning to concepts in different lessons, deepening and enriching them, distinguishing

important features and concepts that exist for a certain age. Therefore, any lesson with an established structure and content can be the basis for integration, the content of which includes a group of concepts related to this topic, knowledge, results of concept analysis. contains z. From the point of view of other subjects, they are involved in integrated lessons and other educational subjects.

For example, the group of concepts "winter", "frost", "cold", "storm" is considered in the lessons of reading, Russian language, natural sciences, music, visual arts.

Thus, integration between academic subjects does not negate the science system. This is a possible way to improve it, eliminate shortcomings, and is aimed at deepening relations and interdependence between subjects.

In a modern school, integration is carried out in several directions and at different levels:

- ✓ within the subject - to combine concepts, knowledge, skills within the framework of separate subjects;
- ✓ interdisciplinary - synthesis of facts, concepts, principles of two or more disciplines;
- ✓ trans-subject - a synthesis of the main and additional components of education.

Transdisciplinary integration is a synthesis of the components of the main and additional content of education.

An example of transdisciplinary integration can be various integrated programs implemented in academic and extracurricular activities, optional and elective courses, creative laboratories, club activities and other directions.

Interdisciplinary integration significantly enriches intradisciplinary.

In fact, in the process of getting to know many facts, interdisciplinary connections are established. Thus, in the mathematics lesson, the topic "Symmetry of bodies" is studied, in the lesson of the surrounding world "Autumn has come", photographs, herbariums of tree leaves (maple, ash) are shown and the questions are discussed: "What is the beauty of leaves?" What is the meaning of symmetry? What is symmetrical?

It helps students to see and understand that symmetry forms exist not only in mathematics, but also in nature and visual arts, and in the technology of making objects of observation.

Conceptual interdisciplinary relations are of particular importance in the formation of natural science concepts.

For example, in the lesson about the surrounding world, children are introduced to the concept of "leafy" and "coniferous" trees. In fine arts classes, this concept is reinforced in drawing branches of deciduous and coniferous trees, in appropriate modeling in technology classes, and the concept is not simply repeated, but associatively reinforced.

Such use of interdisciplinary connections can be called horizontal thematic.

Since integration is not an end in itself, but a specific system of teacher activity, it should solve specific problems of integrated education:

- ✓ increase the level of knowledge of students in the subject, which is manifested in the depth of the acquired concepts and patterns due to the multifaceted interpretation using the information of integral sciences;
- ✓ change the level of intellectual activity by considering the educational material from the position of leading ideas, establishing natural connections between the studied problems;
- ✓ emotional development of students based on the involvement of music, painting, modeling, literature, etc.
- ✓ increase the cognitive interest of students, which is manifested in the desire to work actively and independently in class and outside of class;
- ✓ involving students in creative activities, the result of which can be their own poems, drawings, handicrafts, which reflect a personal attitude to certain events and processes.

Many researchers and practitioners emphasize that it is desirable to integrate subjects in primary school.

The main argument in favor of the integrated approach is that learning subjects through integrated forms of education is compatible with the syncretism of thinking of young students. And this, in turn, lies in the child's perception of the realities of reality as a whole, without distinguishing their details in the whole complex of shapes, colors, sounds and smells.

As the main argument in favor of an integrated approach, the study of subjects through integrated forms of education corresponds to the syncretism (unity, indivisibility, characteristic of the initial state of the development of something) of the thinking of young students, which consists in the child's perception of reality. Reality as a whole, without distinguishing their details in the whole complex of shapes, colors, sounds and smells. It facilitates integrated lessons and a primary teacher teaching all or most subjects in the classroom.

The main feature of an integrated lesson is that such a lesson is based on a single main topic. The rest of the sciences combined with it help to study its connections, processes and the possibilities of applying the acquired knowledge in practice. The structure and content of the lesson will not change.

Integrated lessons in primary school have their own characteristics and, especially in the first grade, they have a collective character, that is, a little bit of everything.

At the initial stage of learning, children get acquainted with many events, concepts, objects, but there are only the simplest ideas about them.

As they learn, they get more new knowledge, supplement and expand the existing ones.

This is mainly the complexity of integrated lessons, because it is necessary to maintain the dynamic development of any topic from introduction to consolidation.

In turn, these lessons allow the teacher to reduce the time spent on individual topics, eliminate the repetition of materials in different subjects, and focus more on the goals (development of speech, thinking) that the teacher emphasizes during learning. allows attention (in various forms).

When conducting integrated lessons, it is necessary to take into account the psychological characteristics of children of primary school age:

- fatigue quickly.

Integrated lessons eliminate fatigue by moving from one activity to another.

- characteristics of dominant forms of perception of young students (visual, auditory, tactile).

In elementary school, integrated lessons combine academic subjects that help develop individual cognitive patterns of each student.

Such integrated lessons have an interdependent form. It is built on the basis of one type of activity, and others are woven into it: cognitive, listening to music, perceiving a picture, artistic work.

The interactive form is often used in primary school.

For example, children are included in play activities in the "Animal Tales" reading lesson outside the classroom. Based on this, the aesthetic activity related to the perception of artistic creation - making paper crafts - origami, theatricalization - is related to the manifestation of oneself in the images of fairy-tale heroes of this work.

Such transfer of the child from one type of activity to another helps to develop his cognitive processes, reduces fatigue by transferring his attention from one type of activity to another. And this, in turn, maintains high performance.

In addition, students playfully practice knowledge, skills and abilities about animal species with the help of an interactive whiteboard. Learn to compare, classify and generalize animals based on their characteristics.

Using a system of interdisciplinary and interdisciplinary tasks from an integrated lesson, creative activities that are a healthy environment, as well as involving the whole class in cognitive team activities that are a healthy creative environment. the key to successful personal development of students.

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